

METAPHORICAL FORMATION OF SOCIO-POLITICAL TERMS: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF UZBEK AND ENGLISH

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ijtimoiy-siyosiy terminlarning metaforik shakllanishi hamda ularning o'zbek va ingliz tillaridagi qiyosiy tahlili keltirilgan. Tadqiqot davomida harbiy, teatr va san'at, texnik, tabiat va ekologiya, shuningdek tibbiyot sohalaridan olingan metaforalarning siyosiy diskursda qo'llanishi tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek, Islom Karimov, Shavkat Mirziyoyev va Barak Obama nutqlaridan hamda BBC, The Guardian kabi manbalardan misollar keltiriladi. Maqolada metaforalarning kognitiv, madaniy va pragmatik yuklamasi, ularni tarjima qilishdagi muammolar va ekvivalentlik masalalari yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: ijtimoiy-siyosiy termin, metafora, dinamik qatlam, siyosiy diskurs, ishintirish ta'siri.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается метафорическое формирование общественно-политических терминов и их сопоставительный анализ в узбекском и английском языках. Исследование выявляет использование метафор, заимствованных из военной, театральной, технической, природной и медицинской сфер, в политическом дискурсе. В качестве примеров приведены речи Ислама Каримова, Шавката Мирзиёева и Барака Обамы, а также материалы BBC и The Guardian. В статье освещаются когнитивные, культурные и прагматические особенности метафор, трудности их перевода и проблема функциональной эквивалентности.

Ключевые слова: общественно-политический термин, метафора, перевод, политический дискурс, сопоставительный анализ.

Abstract: This article examines the metaphorical formation of socio-political terms and their comparative analysis in Uzbek and English. The study explores how metaphors derived from military, theatrical, technical, natural, and medical domains are applied in political discourse. Examples are drawn from the speeches of Islam Karimov, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, and Barack Obama, as well as media sources such as BBC and The Guardian. The article highlights the cognitive, cultural, and pragmatic dimensions of metaphors, discusses translation challenges, and emphasizes the

importance of functional equivalence in rendering socio-political metaphors across languages.

Key words: socio-political term, metaphor, dynamic layer, political discourse, persuasive effect.

Introduction. In the field of linguistics and translation studies, socio-political terminology represents a particularly dynamic layer of vocabulary. Unlike technical terms that are often limited to one field, socio-political terms emerge, develop, and transform within the context of historical, cultural, and ideological changes. One of the most significant mechanisms in the development of socio-political terminology is the use of metaphorical extension, which allows general vocabulary or concepts from other domains to acquire new political meanings.

Metaphor is not only a stylistic device but also a cognitive and pragmatic tool. As G. Lakoff and M. Johnson argue, metaphor plays a fundamental role in human thought, shaping the way we conceptualize abstract phenomena [1:87]. In political discourse, metaphors serve as a means of simplifying complex issues, strengthening ideological positions, and creating persuasive effects.

This article examines the metaphorical formation of socio-political terms in Uzbek and English, highlighting similarities and differences. The analysis draws upon speeches by Uzbek political leaders such as Islam Karimov and Shavkat Mirziyoev, as well as English-language political discourse, including speeches by Barack Obama, materials from the BBC, The Guardian, and other international sources.

Metaphorical Sources of Socio-Political Terms. The metaphorical formation of socio-political terminology can be traced back to several source domains, the most important of which include:

1. Military terminology. Uzbek: *mafkuraviy front* (“ideological front”), *kurash maydoni* (“arena of struggle”). English: battle for hearts and minds, political battlefield.

These metaphors transfer the notion of physical conflict into the ideological and political sphere, emphasizing confrontation and struggle.

2. Theatrical and artistic terminology. Uzbek: *siyosiy sahna* (“political stage”), *soxta niqob* (“false mask”). English: *political stage*, *to wear a mask* in politics. Here *politics* is metaphorically viewed as a performance, with actors (politicians), stage (arena), and spectators (the people).

3. Technical and mechanical terminology. Uzbek: *davlat mashinasi* (“state machinery”), *byurokratik mexanizm* (“bureaucratic mechanism”). English: *state machinery*, *political mechanism*. These metaphors conceptualize the state as a machine requiring regulation, control, and efficiency.

4. Natural and ecological terminology. Uzbek: *inqiroz o'chog'i* (“center of crisis”), *siyosiy girdob* (“political whirlpool”), *hamkorlik ufqlari* (“horizons of cooperation”). English: *winds of change*, *political climate*, *crisis hotspot*. These metaphors present political developments as natural forces, often uncontrollable and dynamic.

5. Medical terminology. Uzbek: *jamiyatdagi illat* (“social disease”), *korrupsiya virusi* (“virus of corruption”). English: *the cancer of corruption*, *political virus*. Political problems are described as diseases threatening the health of society, requiring treatment or eradication.

Studies from Uzbek and English Political Discourse. The Uzbek term *kuch* (“force/power”) illustrates metaphorical polysemy. In everyday usage it denotes physical strength, but in political contexts it may refer to *qurolli kuchlar* (“armed forces”), *siyosiy kuchlar* (“political powers”), or *reaksion kuchlar* (“reactionary forces”). Similarly, in English, *power* and *force* diverge semantically: *power* denotes political authority, while *force* implies military strength [2:64].

Another example is the Uzbek term *xalq* (“the people”), which has both a demographic and a political meaning. In Shavkat Mirziyoyev’s UN speech (2021), the phrase *xalq ishonchi* (“the trust of the people”) refers to legitimacy derived from popular support.

In English, Barack Obama frequently used the expression the American *people* expect... to highlight democratic accountability. Although both refer to collective citizens, the semantic scope of *people* and *nation* in English does not fully match the Uzbek *xalq*.

Metaphorical expressions such as *siyosiy portlash* (“political explosion”) or *axborot bozori* (“information market”) illustrate the productive use of metaphors in Uzbek political texts. Their equivalents in English, *political explosion* and *information marketplace*, carry similar imagery and demonstrate parallel processes of semantic extension.

Comparative Findings. The comparative analysis shows that:

1. Both Uzbek and English political discourses rely heavily on metaphors from military, theatrical, technical, natural, and medical domains.
2. Some metaphors are universal (political arena, state machinery), reflecting common cognitive models.
3. Other metaphors are culture-specific: Uzbek *mahalla* has no direct English equivalent, while English *checks and balances* requires explanatory translation into Uzbek.

4. In translation, the ideological load and pragmatic function of metaphors must be preserved, not just their literal meaning.

Conclusion. Metaphorical formation plays a vital role in enriching socio-political terminology in both Uzbek and English. By transferring concepts from other domains into politics, metaphors allow abstract and complex processes to be conceptualized in accessible, persuasive terms. For translators, the challenge lies in ensuring functional equivalence—retaining the metaphor's cognitive, cultural, and pragmatic resonance. Literal translation may convey the image but fail to communicate its ideological impact. Therefore, a balanced approach that combines semantic fidelity with cultural adaptation is required.

This comparative study reveals that while many metaphorical socio-political terms overlap across languages, cultural specificity often demands creative translation strategies.

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